

ISic0362

I.Sicily inscription 0362

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

convento di San Francesco dei Padri Minori Conventuali

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3549

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · M(anibus) ·
2. Numonia ·
3. Alexandria ·
4. vix(it) ann(is) XXV

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 with photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld, Numonia from Alexandria, lived 25 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491573

EDR 141208

EDCS 21900402

PHI 313674

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7080 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2005.0670

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias 7*. Messina. At 42

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